

A Study To Assess The Effectiveness Of Video Assisted Teaching Programme On Knowledge Regarding Postpartum Depression Among Primi Antenatal Mothers In Selected Hospitals At Kollam

P. V. Greeshma*, Anna Cardoz, Ashna N., Josmi J., Lekshmi S. Lal, Vijee J.

Bishop Benziger College of Nursing, P. B. No. 46, Sastri Junction, Kollam 691001, Kerala.

ABSTRACT

Background of the study: Postpartum depression (PPD) is a serious public health concern that affects millions of women around the world. It is a complex condition that affects the mother's mental and physical health, her relationships, and her capacity to raise children. It is characterized by persistent emotions of sadness, hopelessness, and worry after giving birth. **Methodology:** An pre-experimental research design was used. A total of 60 samples were selected by purposive sampling technique. The tool used in this study was self-structured knowledge questionnaire. The data was analysed with descriptive and inferential statistics. **Results:** The present study is aimed to assess the effectiveness of video assisted teaching program on knowledge regarding Postpartum Depression among primi antenatal mothers in selected hospitals at Kollam. The study result shows mean post-test knowledge score of pre-experimental group (17.5 ± 1.5) was higher than mean pre-test knowledge score (7.283 ± 3.36) and calculated 't' value is greater than the table value at 0.05 level of significance. It indicates that there was significant improvement in the knowledge of Postpartum Depression among primi antenatal mothers .and calculated 't' value is greater than table value at 0.05 level of significance ($p < 0.05$). **Conclusion:** The present study shows that video assisted teaching program was effective in improving knowledge of Postpartum Depression among primi antenatal mothers.

Keywords: Postpartum depression, video assisted teaching programme, primi antenatal mother's.

INTRODUCTION

Postpartum depression (PPD) is a serious public health concern that affects millions of women around the world. It is a complex condition that affects the mother's mental and physical health, her relationships, and her capacity to raise children. It is characterized by persistent emotions of sadness, hopelessness, and worry after giving birth. 1

The prevalence of postpartum depression (PPD) in India is between 11% and 40%, according to studies. Postpartum depression affects 10–20% of postpartum women worldwide, with varying prevalence. If untreated, PPD can lead to severe consequences, including a lower quality of life, strained relationships with friends and family, an increased likelihood of suicidal thoughts and actions, and impaired bonding between mother and infant as well as delayed cognitive and emotional development in infants. 2

Early detection and intervention are crucial for preventing and managing postpartum depression. Antenatal education and support can greatly assist expectant mothers in reducing their risk of postpartum depression and in preparing for the challenges of parenting. Many prenatal education programs provide inadequate information on postpartum depression (PPD), its prevention, and treatment, despite the importance of early intervention. Healthcare practitioners frequently employ traditional teaching methods, which may not be engaging or effective for retaining information. 3

The purpose of this study is to assess the effectiveness of a video-assisted teaching program (VATP) in enhancing antenatal mothers' knowledge and prevention of postpartum depression (PPD). By addressing the current gaps in prenatal education and supporting the development of effective postpartum depression prevention and treatment strategies, the

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

video assisted teaching programme will provide a novel and engaging approach to education.⁴

Objectives

- To assess the knowledge regarding postpartum depression among primi antenatal mothers in selected hospitals at Kollam.
- To assess the effectiveness of the video assisted teaching programme on knowledge regarding postpartum depression among primi antenatal mothers.
- To find the association between pretest knowledge scores with selected demographic variables (Age, type of family, area of residence, education, occupation, average menstrual days and previous history of postpartum depression in the family).

Operational definition

Assess: In this study assess refers to determine the knowledge regarding postpartum depression among primi antenatal mothers in selected hospital at Kollam.

Effectiveness: In this study, it refers to change in knowledge level of primi antenatal mothers regarding postpartum depression after video assisted teaching programme.

Video assisted teaching programme: it refers to a multimedia teaching in a systematically organized way with the help of video to provide information to primi antenatal mothers on postpartum depression and its prevention.

Knowledge: In this study knowledge refers to information regarding postpartum depression assessed by a knowledge questionnaire among primi antenatal mothers in selected hospitals at Kollam.

Postpartum depression: In this study it refers to a medical condition causing a woman to feel very sad and anxious after giving birth, often accompanied by negative thoughts and difficulty dealing with normal life.

Primi Antenatal mother: In this study it refers to a pregnant woman who is receiving healthcare and support during her pregnancy.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A cross-sectional study carried out in Argentina in 2016 examined the prevalence of postpartum depression among low-income women receiving care at public hospitals. The research included 539 participants who were evaluated four weeks after giving birth using the Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS). Results indicated that 31% of the women showed signs of depression (EPDS score of 10 or higher), with 18.4% experiencing moderate to severe symptoms (EPDS score of 13 or above). Key risk factors identified were a history of mental illness, unemployment, being a single mother, and limited social support. The study concluded that financial challenges and prior psychiatric conditions significantly increase the likelihood of postpartum depression in urban areas of Latin America.

A cross-sectional study was conducted in 2024 among 200 postnatal mothers attending a tertiary care hospital in Mangalore, Karnataka, to assess the prevalence and psychosocial risk factors associated with postpartum depression. The participants were selected using convenient sampling, and the Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS) was administered. The study found that 34% of mothers were at risk of PPD. Key contributing factors included low socioeconomic status, lack of education, semi- or unskilled occupations, unwanted pregnancy, complications during pregnancy, absence of the husband at childbirth, and pressure to deliver a female child. The study concluded that early detection and support for modifiable psychosocial factors could significantly reduce the incidence of postpartum depression.

A cross-sectional study involving 1,517 pregnant women in Peru assessed the reliability and validity of two depression screening tools: the PHQ-9 and the EPDS. Both instruments demonstrated high internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha values above 0.8. The two scales were moderately correlated ($\rho \approx 0.52$), but their underlying factor structures varied: the PHQ-9 emphasized somatic symptoms, while the EPDS was more associated with anxiety-related depressive symptoms. Agreement between the tools was moderate, with a kappa coefficient of 0.46. Based on these outcomes, the researchers suggested that using

both tools together could enhance the detection of depression.

A cross-sectional survey of 279 postpartum mothers attending a paediatric tertiary care centre in Mumbai assessed PPD literacy using a structured questionnaire. Only 50.7% of mothers demonstrated adequate knowledge about symptoms, causative factors, and help-seeking behaviours. Knowledge levels were significantly associated with older age, higher income, and professional occupation. The authors highlighted the urgent need to sensitize postpartum women through educational interventions.

A dose response meta-analysis (2022) of physical activity and risk of PPD across ~186,000 women globally. This study analysed RCTs and prospective cohort data, assessing physical activity during pregnancy and postpartum with respect to PPD incidence measured by EPDS or equivalent tools. They found moderate-to-vigorous activity significantly reduced PPD risk (adjusted OR \approx 0.73), with protective effects plateauing at ~90 minutes/week. Sports-type and structured exercise contributed most; household or incidental activity less so. They concluded that prescribed moderate exercise during and after pregnancy is an effective preventive strategy against PPD.

A quasi-experimental cohort study conducted in Pelotas, Brazil in 2021 examined the preventive impact of brief cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) on postpartum depression in women identified as at-risk during pregnancy. A total of 193 women without current depression but showing vulnerability participated in a six-session group CBT course delivered by trained non-specialists. EPDS scores were assessed during pregnancy and postpartum. The intervention group had lower rates of postpartum depression (5.5%) than controls (2.2%). The authors concluded that low-intensity CBT during pregnancy is an effective preventive tool for managing PPD risk in low-resource settings.

METHODOLOGY

Research Approach: Quantitative research approach

Research Design: Pre-experimental research design.

Research Variables:

Independent variable: In the present study independent variable was the video assisted teaching programme.

Dependant variable: In the present study, dependent variables knowledge regarding postpartum depression among primi antenatal mothers in selected hospitals at Kollam.

Demographic variables

In this study demographic variables were age, type of family, area of residence, education, occupation, average menstrual day, and previous history of postpartum depression in the family.

Research setting: The setting selected for the present study was AGC Hospital Kollam and Bishop Benziger Hospital Kollam

Sample: Primi antenatal mother's

Sample size and sampling technique: 60 samples and a purposive sampling technique

Tools:

Demographic Performa

Self structured knowledge questionnaire

Data analysis

Data obtained was entered into a master sheet and analyzed by descriptive and inferential statistics. The data was presented in figures and tables

- Demographic data was analysed using frequency and percentage.
- The effect of video assisted teaching program on knowledge regarding post-partum depression among primi antenatal mothers was analysed using paired 't' test.
- Association between the pre-test knowledge scores with selected demographic variables was analysed using chi-square test.

RESULTS

Description of sample characteristics

- The data of age distribution shows that out of 60 samples (65%) belongs to the age group of 18-25

years, and (35%) belongs to the age group of 26-30 years.

□ According to the type of family, (75%) belong to nuclear family and remaining samples (25%) belong to joint family.

□ It exposes that most of the samples (50%) were residing in the rural areas, and samples (48%) were residing in the urban areas and remaining samples (2%) were residing in the semi urban areas.

□ With regard to education status, it is observed that (48%) had either graduation and above, (43%) higher secondary education, (7%) had high school education and Only (2%) of them had primary education.

□ Its highlight that most of the sample (77%) had no previous history of postpartum depression in the family and only (23%) had the previous history of postpartum depression in the family.

□ With regard to menstrual days, it is observed that most of the sample (65%) of the sample had 3-5 days of menstruation, (22%) had 6-8 days of menstruation, (10%) had 1-2 days of menstruation and remaining (3%) had 9-12 days of menstruation.

□ It shows that most of the samples (50%) of samples belongs to private job, (33%) of sample belongs to self-employee, (10%) of sample belongs to business and remaining (7%) of sample belongs to government job.

Description of pretest knowledge scores among pre-experimental group

The data shows that in the pre-experimental group (27%) had poor knowledge and (58%) had average knowledge and (15%) had good knowledge. The mean of the pre-experimental group was (7.283) with standard deviation of (3.36).

Description of post-test knowledge scores among pre-experimental group

The data shows that in the pre-experimental group (90%) had very good knowledge and (10%) had good knowledge. The mean of the experiment group was (17.5) with standard deviation of (1.5).

Effectiveness of video assisted teaching program on knowledge regarding postpartum depression among primi antenatal mothers.

□ The mean pre-test knowledge score of primi antenatal mothers on postpartum depression was 7.67 and the mean post-test knowledge score of primi antenatal mothers on postpartum depression was 17.8. It indicates the effectiveness of video assisted teaching programme on knowledge regarding postpartum depression among primi antenatal mothers. Hence, the hypothesis, H2 which states that there will be significant difference between pre-test and post-test score on knowledge regarding postpartum depression among primi antenatal mothers was accepted.

□ The calculated t value was 22.74 and the tabulated t value was 2.00. the calculated t value is greater than the tabulated t value at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that the video assisted teaching programme was effective in improving the knowledge of primi antenatal mothers regarding postpartum depression. Hence the hypothesis, H1 which states that there would be significant difference between pre-test and post-test knowledge scores on knowledge of postpartum depression among primi antenatal mothers is accepted.

Association between pre-test knowledge scores of samples with selected demographic variables such as age, type of family, areas of residence, education, previous history in the family, menstrual days, occupation.

The association between the pre-test knowledge scores with selected demographic variables such as age, type of family, areas of residence, education, previous history in the family, menstrual days, occupation were computed by chi-square test. The calculated chi-square value for age was 0.6511 which is less than tabulated chi-square value (5.991) and the calculated chi-square value for type of family was 1.0937 which is less than the tabulated chi-square value (5.991). The calculated chi-square value for area of residence was 3.7217 which is less than tabulated chi-square value (5.991). The calculated chi-square value for education is 5.7348 which is less than the tabulated value (12.592). The calculated chi-square value for previous history in the family is 0.9624 which is less than the tabulated chi-square

value (5.991). The calculated chi-square value for menstrual days was 3.6659 which is less than the tabulated chi-square value (12.592). The calculated chi-square value for occupation was 5.7843 which is less than tabulated value (12.592). Therefore, the pretest knowledge score did not have significant association with the demographic variables such as age, type of family, area of residence, education, previous history in the family, menstrual days, occupation. Hence, the research hypothesis, H2 which states that there no significant association between pre-test knowledge scores and the demographic variables such as age, type of family, area of residence, education, previous history in the family, menstrual days, occupation was rejected.

CONCLUSION

The present study is aimed to assess the effectiveness of video assisted teaching program on knowledge regarding Postpartum Depression among primi antenatal mothers in selected hospitals at Kollam. The study result shows mean posttest knowledge score of pre-experimental group (17.5 ± 1.5) was higher than mean pretest knowledge score (7.283 ± 3.36) and calculated 't' value is greater than the table value at 0.05 level of significance. It indicates that there was significant improvement in the knowledge of Postpartum Depression among primi antenatal mothers .and calculated 't' value is greater than table value at 0.05 level of significance ($p < 0.05$). So, the present study shows that video assisted teaching program was effective in improving knowledge of Postpartum Depression among primi antenatal mothers.

REFERENCES

- O'Hara MW, McCabe JE. Postpartum depression: current status and future directions. *Annu Rev Clin Psychol.* 2013; 9:379–407.
- Upadhyay RP, Chowdhury R, Salehi A, Sarkar K, Singh SK, Sinha B. Postpartum depression in India: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Bull World Health Organ.* 2017;95(10):706–17C.
- Shorey S, Chee CYI, Ng ED, Chan YH, Tam WWS, Chong YS. Prevalence and incidence of postpartum depression among healthy mothers: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Psychiatry Res.* 2018; 253:373–85.
- Slomian J, Honvo G, Emonts P, Reginster JY, Bruyère O. Consequences of maternal postpartum depression: a systematic review of maternal and infant outcomes. *Womens Health (Lond).* 2019; 15:1745506519844044.
- Leach LS, Poyser C, Fairweather-Schmidt AK. Maternal perinatal anxiety: A review of prevalence and correlates. *Clin Psychol.* 2017;21(1):4–19.
- Rajeswari S, Sanjeevareddy N. Effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge regarding postpartum depression among antenatal mothers. *Int J Community Med Public Health.* 2020;7(2):619–23
- Sockol LE. A systematic review of the efficacy of cognitive-behavioral therapy for treating and preventing perinatal depression. *J Affect Disord.* 2015; 177:7–21.
- SharmaKS.Nursingresearchandstatistics. 2nded.NewDelhi: Elsevier;2014
- SharmaKS.Nursingresearchandstatistics. 2nded.NewDelhi: Elsevier;2014
- Santos DS, Santos DN, Silva RdeC, Silva SG, Barreto ML, Oliveira NF. Post-partum depression: A cross-sectional study of women enrolled in a conditional cash transfer program in 30 Brazilian cities. *J Affect Disord.* 2021 Feb 1; 281:999–1005. Doi: 10.1016/j.jad.2020.11.126. PMID: 33388462.
- Silva RA, Jansen K, Souza LD, Moraes IG, Tomasi E, Silva FP, et al. Sociodemographic risk factors of perinatal depression: a cohort study in the public health care system. *Rev Bras Psiquiatr.* 2012 Jun;34(2):143–8. Doi:10.1590/S1516-44462012000200005. PMID: 22729409.
- Melo EF Jr, Cecatti JG, Pacagnella RC, Leite DF, Vulcani DE, Makuch MY. The prevalence of perinatal depression and its associated factors in two different settings in Brazil. *J Affect Disord.* 2012 Mar;136(3):1204–8. Doi: 10.1016/j.jad.2011.11.032. PMID: 22169251.
- Santos DS, Silva Filho IG, Silva RA, Osório AAC. Mental health of postpartum women during the COVID-19 pandemic in Brazil. *PsicolTeor Prat.* 2023;25(2): ePTPCP14807. Doi:10.5935/1980-6906/ePTPCP14807.en.
- Pham D, Cormick G, Amyx MM, Gibbons L, Doty M, Brown A, Norwood A, Daray FM, Althabe F, Belizán JM. Factors associated with

postpartum depression in women from low socioeconomic level in Argentina: a hierarchical model approach. *J Affect Disord.* 2018 Feb; 227:731–738. Doi: 10.1016/j.jad.2017.11.091. PMID: 29179143.

HOW TO CITE: P. V. Greeshma*, Anna Cardoz, Ashna N., Josmi J., Lekshmi S. Lal, Vijee J., A Study To Assess The Effectivenss Of Video Assisted Teaching Programme On Knowledge Regarding Postpartum Depression Among Primi Antenatal Mothers In Selected Hospitals At Kollam, *Int. J. Sci. R. Tech.*, 2026, 3 (5), 750-755. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20321503>